

Studies in Reductions with Vanadium (II)

Part III : Potentiometric Titration of Molybdenum (VI) with Vanadium (II) in presence of Manganese [III] and cerium [IV]

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Potentiometric titration of Mo(VI) in presence of Ce (IV) or Mn (III) against vanadium (II) has been performed in the atmosphere of nitrogen and in this case the presence of phosphoric acid is not essential for fast reaction. Potential breaks indicate that effective reduction of Mo (VI) takes place along with vanadium (IV) formed as the intermediate product. Between 7N to 12N sulphuric acid Mo (VI) is reduced to Mo (III) and between 2N to 6N it is reduced to Mo (V) state. It is also found that Mo (VI) can be quantitatively and easily reduced at ordinary temperature if Mn^{++} or Ce^{+++} ions in small quantity is used as catalyst. In this case two potential breaks are obtained between 7N to 12N sulphuric acid corresponding to Mo (V) and Mo (III) and only one break between 2N to 6N which corresponds to Mo (V). Below 2N sulphuric acid titrations are not possible, probably due to formation of molybdenum blue.

WE have already reported¹ that when vanadium (II) solution was added to molybdenum (VI) solution, from visual observations the reaction seemed to be slow. But on addition of about 1 ml. of phosphoric acid, the reaction was fast as Mo (VI) becomes more reducible probably due to the formation of phosphomolybdate complex². Cr (II) solution with almost identical oxidation potential has been found by Platt and Sommer³ to reduce Mo (VI) successively to MoO^{+++} or MoO^+ in presence of other oxidants namely W (VI), V (V), Ti (IV), Fe (III) or Cu (II) in hydrochloric or sulphuric acid medium. Brintzinger and co-workers^{4,5} have reported the same results when a binary mixture of Fe(III) and Mo (VI) was reduced with Cr (II) solution. Dickens and Brennecke⁶ have also studied the reductions of binary mixtures of Mo (VI) and V (V) with Sn (II) as reducing agent. Recently Chawla and Tandon^{7,8} applied vanadium (II) sulphate for analysis of binary mixtures of ceric, dichromate, vanadate and vanadyl. There is no evidence for reduction of molybdate with vanadium (II) sulphate or chloride in presence of other oxidants or ions. Hence it was thought to investigate the reduction of molybdenum (VI) by vanadium (II) sulphate in presence of other oxidants namely Mn (III) and Ce (IV), which are themselves reduced quantitatively by vanadium (II) sulphate⁹.

Experimental

Vanadium (II) solution :

It was prepared, stored and standardised as reported earlier⁹.

Molybdenum (VI) solution :

It was prepared by dissolving sodium molybdate (B.D.H.) in air-free distilled water and standardised¹⁰.

Cerium (IV) solution :

It was prepared in air-free distilled water by using B.D.H. sample of pure ceric hydroxide and was standardised against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution.

Manganese (III) solution :

The reported method¹¹ for the preparation of Mn (III) sulphate was modified by using double the acid concentration to avoid the precipitation of MnO_2 during the reaction. The stock solution was prepared in 14N sulphuric acid and solution in lower acid concentration was prepared by diluting upto 8N H_2SO_4 . Below this acid concentration Mn (III) solution was not sufficiently stable. This fact was also supported by Gupta and Ghose¹². It was standardised against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution at the end of each titration.

Vanadium (IV) solution :

Vanadyl sulphate (B.D.H.) was used for preparing the solution in air-free distilled water and concentrated sulphuric acid (A.R.) was added to give the desired acid concentration. It was standardised by standard potassium permanganate solution.

Manganese (II) and Cerium (III) solution :

Manganese sulphate (G.R.) was used for preparing Mn(II) solution and Ce(III) solution was prepared by passing Ce(IV) solution through Jone's reductor.

The cell was deoxygenated by passing nitrogen gas for 15 to 20 min. before taking a known volume of the mixture of oxidants. The requisite amount of sulphuric acid and air-free distilled water was added so

as to make the desired acidity and also an initial constant volume (20 ml.) was maintained. Vanadium (II) solution was added from the burette and the stable potentials were noted after each addition. Other experimental details are same as reported in the previous paper¹. Experimental results are given in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Results and Discussions

When Mo(VI) solution along with measured quantity of other oxidants Mn(III) or Ce(IV) was taken in the cell containing sulphuric acid, from visual observations the reaction with vanadium(II) seems to be fast. The initial cherry red [Mo(VI) + Mn(III)] or yellow [Mo(VI) + Ce(IV)] colour faded as vanadium(II) solution was added and the colours at the three inflexion points in each titration was pale yellow, blue and greenish blue respectively upto acid concentration of 7N. Below 7N there was reddish brown colouration at the third inflexion point.

With manganese(III) in the reaction mixture, acid concentration below 8N was not used as it is unstable, whereas titrations were performed in 2N to 12N sulphuric acid; when Ce(IV) was present in the mixture. Titration below 2N is not possible because of the formation of molybdenum blue. Also the indicator electrode starts behaving erratically in this acid concentration range. The colour of the solution in the cell and the consumption of vanadium(II) at the three inflexion points corresponds to equations I, III and IV + VI; when oxidant mixture contained Mo(VI) and Mn(III), and to equations II, III and IV + VI, when Mo(VI) and Ce(IV) in 7N to 12N H₂SO₄ was taken in the cell. The equations II, III and IV + V accounts for three inflexion points in 2N to 6N H₂SO₄ (Table 1). Since stable ionic specie of Mo(IV) are not known to exist in solution the reduction of molybdenum(VI) to this state is not possible and also the stoichiometries in different acid concentrations does not indicate the formation of Mo(IV) specie.

Thus it seems that the effective reduction of molybdenum(VI) and vanadium(IV) takes place with almost the same equilibrium constant which is also expected from thermodynamic considerations. At the same time it may also be assumed that reduction of molybdenum(VI) is catalysed by vanadium

TABLE 1. POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN PRESENCE OF MN(III), CE(IV) AND VO²⁺

S.No.	X(N) (H ₂ SO ₄)	Amount of vanadium(II) at three inflexions. (1 × 10 ⁻⁴ moles)					
		Required			Consumed		
		I	II	III	I	II	III
(A) Manganese(III)							
1.	12N	1.03	1.55	3.41	1.03	1.53	3.41
2.	10N	1.03	1.55	3.41	1.03	1.54	3.41
3.	8N	1.03	1.55	3.41	1.03	1.54	3.41
(B) Cerium(IV)							
4.	12N	0.33	0.49	2.04	0.33	0.50	2.04
5.	10N	0.33	0.49	2.04	0.33	0.50	2.04
6.	7N	0.33	0.49	2.04	0.33	0.50	2.04
7.	2N	0.33	0.49	1.12	0.33	0.50	1.14
(C) Vanadium(IV)							
8.	10N	—	—	2.24	—	—	2.25
9.	2N	—	—	1.33	—	—	1.33

TABLE 2. POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION IN PRESENCE OF MN(II) AND CE(III)

S.No.	Catalyst	X(N)	Amount of vanadium(II) solution (1 × 10 ⁻⁴ moles)			
			Required		Consumed	
			I	II	I	II
1.	Mn(II)	12N	0.46	1.38	0.46	1.38
2.		10N	0.46	1.38	0.46	1.38
3.		7N	0.46	1.38	0.46	1.37
4.		6N	0.46	—	0.46	—
5.		2N	0.46	—	0.46	—
6.	Ce(III)	12N	0.46	1.38	0.46	1.38
7.		10N	0.46	1.38	0.46	1.37
8.		7N	0.46	1.38	0.46	1.38
9.		6N	0.46	—	0.46	—
10.		2N	0.46	—	0.46	—

TABLE 3. ANALYSIS OF BINARY MIXTURES

Oxidants	Moles of oxidant 10 ⁻⁶			Moles of molybdenum(VI) 10 ⁻⁶		
	Taken	Found	Error %	Taken	Found	Error %
(a) Manganese(III)	154.5	154.2	-0.2	45.0	45.2	+0.4
	104.0	104.8	+0.8	91.8	92.4	+0.6
(b) Cerium(IV)	100.0	99.0	-1.0	45.9	45.7	-0.4
	51.0	51.4	+0.8	91.8	91.3	-0.5
(c) Vanadium(IV)	86.7	86.5	-0.2	45.9	46.2	+0.6
	173.5	174.8	+0.8	91.8	92.0	-0.4

(IV), manganese (II) or cerium (III) species. In order to arrive at this conclusion reduction of molybdenum (VI) different acid concentrations were done in presence of vanadium (IV), manganese (II) or cerium (III) solution. As per experimental data given in the Table 1 Mo (VI) solution in presence of vanadium (IV) was reduced to MoO^+ (equation VI) stage in acid concentration $7N$ to $12N$ and MoO_2^+ stage

ordinary temperature by potentiometric titrations in presence of Mn^{3+} , Ce^{4+} and VO^{2+} ions. Some typical results on the analysis of binary mixtures of Mo (VI) with Mn (III), Ce (IV) and V (IV) by vanadium (II) are given in Table 3. In case of V (IV)+Mo (VI) mixture, the VO^{3+} has been estimated by potentiometric method using cerium (IV). The difference gives the amount of Mo (VI) in the mixture.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves.

- 5 ml. $0.918 \times 10^{-2}M$ molybdenum(VI) in presence of—
- (i) 5 ml. $0.309 \times 10^{-2}M$ manganese(III) in $8N$ H_2SO_4 (Curve A);
 - (ii) 10 ml. $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ Ce(IV) in $10N$ H_2SO_4 (Curve B), in $2N$ H_2SO_4 (Curve C);
 - (iii) 10 ml. $0.867 \times 10^{-2}M$ vanadium(IV) in $10N$ H_2SO_4 (Curve D) in $2N$ H_2SO_4 (Curve E);
 - (iv) 0.5 ml. $1.0 \times 10^{-5}M$ manganese(II) in $10N$ H_2SO_4 (Curve F) in $2N$ H_2SO_4 (Curve G);
 - (v) 0.5 ml. $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ cerium(II) in $10N$ H_2SO_4 (Curve H) in $2N$ H_2SO_4 (Curve I).

(equation V) in $2N$ to $6N$ H_2SO_4 . Molybdenum (VI) solution was also reduced quickly in presence of Mn^{2+} or Ce^{3+} ions (Table 2). Between $2N$ to $6N$ acid concentration the inflexion point accounts for reduction of molybdenum (VI) to MoO_2^+ but in $7N$ to $12N$ H_2SO_4 the first inflexion point corresponds to formation of MoO_2^+ (equation V) and second one to formation of Mo^{3+} (equation VII). A few typical titration curves are given in the figure. Only a small amount of (about 0.05×10^{-4} moles) Ce^{3+} or Mn^{2+} was needed to catalyse the reduction of Mo (VI). Below ($2N$) acid concentration the formation of molybdenum blue interferes and requires much more time to attain the stable equilibrium.

Thus it is seen that between $2N$ to $12N$ sulphuric acid the reduction of molybdate with vanadium (II) sulphate does not require phosphoric acid. The Mn^{2+} , Ce^{3+} or VO^{2+} ions may be employed as catalyst for easy and quantitative reduction of molybdate. Also molybdate can be quantitatively analysed at

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